

Reactions of aniline with unsymmetrical acid anhydrides

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Reaction of aniline with some mixed/unsymmetrical acid anhydrides to give exclusively one of the anilides is described.

In an earlier communication¹, we reported the synthesis of various acid anhydrides. We now report the results of our study on the reactions of unsymmetrical acid anhydrides with aniline with a view to determine if any selectivity exists in the formation of anilides. Aniline was chosen as a reference nucleophile because of the reactivity of its nitrogen towards electrophiles like acylating agents and the ease for characterisation of the products.

Results and Discussion

The independent reaction of aniline in chloroform solution at room temperature with unsymmetrical benzoic anhydrides like benzoic-*p*-chlorobenzoic, benzoic-*p*-nitrobenzoic and benzoic-3,5-dinitrobenzoic anhydrides yielded in each case the corresponding substituted benzanilides only, i.e. *p*-chlorobenzanilide, *p*-nitrobenzanilide and 3,5-dinitrobenzanilide (sl. nos. 1, 3 and 5 of Table 1). No evidence for the

formation of the other anilide, i.e. benzanilide could be found on TLC comparison of the reaction mixtures or products with authentic samples. On the other hand, reaction with the unsymmetrical anhydrides, benzoic-*p*-methyl and benzoic-*m*-methoxybenzoic anhydrides under identical conditions gave, in both cases, the unsubstituted benzanilides only (sl. nos. 2 and 4 of Table 1).

Similarly, reaction of aniline with mixed anhydrides of the sulfonic-carboxylic anhydrides type such as benzenesulfonic-benzoic, benzenesulfonic-*p*-chlorobenzoic, benzenesulfonic-*p*-methylbenzoic, benzenesulfonic-*p*-nitrobenzoic and benzenesulfonic-*m*-methoxybenzoic anhydrides gave benzocarboxylic anilides alone (sl. nos. 6-10 of Table 1). In case of reaction of aniline with mixed anhydrides of acetic-benzoic anhydride types, namely, acetic-benzoic, acetic-*p*-chlorobenzoic, acetic-*p*-methylbenzoic, acetic-*p*-nitrobenzoic and acetic-*m*-methoxybenzoic anhydrides, acetanilides

Table 1. Reactions of aniline with mixed acid anhydrides*

Sl. no.	Mixed anhydride used	Anilide obtained	M.p. ^a , °C
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -Cl (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -Cl (<i>p</i>)	190-92 (194)
2.	C ₆ H ₅ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₅	162-63 (162)
3.	C ₆ H ₅ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	213-15 (211)
4.	C ₆ H ₅ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₅	164-65 (162)
5.	C ₆ H ₅ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₃ -(NO ₂) ₂ (<i>m,m'</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₃ -(NO ₂) ₂ (<i>m,m'</i>)	231-32 (234)
6.	C ₆ H ₅ -SO ₂ -O-CO-C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₅	160-62 (162)
7.	C ₆ H ₅ -SO ₂ -O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -Cl (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -Cl (<i>p</i>)	192-93 (194)
8.	C ₆ H ₅ -SO ₂ -O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	144-45 (148)
9.	C ₆ H ₅ -SO ₂ -O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	208-09 (211)
10.	C ₆ H ₅ -SO ₂ -O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	117-18
11.	CH ₃ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-CH ₃	112-14 (113)
12.	CH ₃ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -Cl (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-CH ₃	111-12 (113)
13.	CH ₃ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-CH ₃	110-12 (113)
14.	CH ₃ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ (<i>p</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-CH ₃	113-14 (113)
15.	CH ₃ -CO-O-CO-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	C ₆ H ₅ -NH-CO-CH ₃	110-11 (113)

*Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained. ^aLit. value (Ref. 3) in parenthesis.

were isolated exclusively (sl. nos. 11-15 of Table 1) in each case.

The above reactions may be explained on the basis of electronic factors preferring attack by the nucleophile (i.e. aniline) on one of the carbonyl carbons of the anhydride as also the leaving group capabilities of the anion. The reactivity of mixed anhydrides having aryl sulfonic acids as one of the components is, of course, well known in the literature².

Experimental

All m.ps. were determined in a sulfuric acid bath in open capillaries and are uncorrected. TLC analyses were carried out using silica gel-G and visualisation was done by exposing the plates to iodine vapours/UV-light. IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT-IR 5300 spectrometer. HPLC analysis was carried out using a Shimadzu LC 10 AT instrument using methanol as the mobile phase and Hypersil as column. The preparation and melting points of various acid anhydrides used in this work have been described earlier¹.

Reaction of aniline with acid anhydrides. General pro-

cedure : To a solution of aniline (0.91 ml, 10 mmol) in chloroform (20 ml) was added the respective acid anhydride (10 mmol) in chloroform at RT for 10 min. After the completion (TLC check) of the reaction (~0.5 h), the chloroform solution was evaporated and the residue triturated with *n*-hexane to obtain a hexane-insoluble product, which was found to be the anilide. The supernatant hexane solution was then evaporated to obtain a residue which was found to be the carboxylic acid. The crude anilides thus obtained (yields 95–98%) were crystallised from suitable solvents.

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References

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